

Original Article

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**PREVALENCE OF UPPER AND LOWER
RESPIRATORY TRACT INFECTIONS IN
PATIENTS PRESENTING IN MEDICAL
OUTDOOR**

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ABSTRACT:

An upper respiratory tract infection (URTI) is an illness caused by an acute infection, which involves the upper respiratory tract, including the nose, sinuses, pharynx, larynx, or trachea. Lower respiratory tract infection (LRTI) is a term often used as a synonym for pneumonia but can also be applied to other types of infection including lung abscess and acute bronchitis. The objective of this study is to evaluate the prevalence of upper and lower respiratory tract infection among patients presenting in medical outdoor department. This study was conducted among the patients presenting in the medical outdoor department of different hospitals. Name, age, gender and history and duration of respiratory tract infection were noted on a predefined proforma. The mean age of the patients was 34.98 ± 4.23 years. There were 43 males and 55 females. There were 15 (35%) males and 42 (65%) females who presented with upper respiratory tract infections. There were 29 (65%) males and 13 (24%) females presented with lower respiratory tract infections. The mean duration of infection was 5.78 ± 2.34 days.

Keyword: Upper respiratory infection, lower respiratory infection

INTRODUCTION:

An upper respiratory tract infection (URTI) is an illness caused by an acute infection, which involves the upper respiratory tract, including the nose, sinuses, pharynx, larynx, or trachea. This commonly includes nasal obstruction, sore throat, tonsillitis, pharyngitis, laryngitis, sinusitis, otitis media, and the common cold. Most infections are viral in nature, and in other instances, the cause is bacterial. URTIs can also be fungal or helminthic in origin, but these are less common. In 2015, 17.2 billion cases of URTIs are estimated to have occurred. In uncomplicated colds, coughing and nasal discharge may persist for 14 days or more even after other symptoms have resolved. Acute URTIs include rhinitis, pharyngitis/tonsillitis, and laryngitis often referred to as a common cold, and their complications: sinusitis, ear infection, and sometimes bronchitis (though bronchi are generally classified as part of the lower respiratory tract.) Symptoms of URTIs commonly include cough, sore throat, runny nose, nasal congestion, headache, low-grade fever, facial pressure, and sneezing. Symptoms of rhinovirus in children usually begin 1–3 days after exposure. The illness usually lasts 7–10 more days. Color or consistency changes in mucous discharge to yellow, thick, or green are the natural course of viral URTI and not an indication for antibiotics. Group A beta-hemolytic streptococcal pharyngitis/tonsillitis (strep throat) typically presents with a sudden onset of sore throat, pain with swallowing, and fever. Strep throat does not usually cause runny nose, voice changes, or cough. Pain and pressure of the ear caused by a middle-ear infection (otitis media) and the reddening of the eye caused by viral conjunctivitis are often associated with URTIs. Lower respiratory tract infection (LRTI) is a term often used as a synonym for pneumonia but can also be applied to other types of infection including lung abscess and acute bronchitis. Symptoms include shortness of breath, weakness, fever, coughing and fatigue. A routine chest X-ray is not always necessary for people who have symptoms of a lower respiratory tract infection. Influenza affects both the upper and lower respiratory tracts. Antibiotics are the first line treatment for pneumonia; however, they are

neither effective nor indicated for parasitic or viral infections (1-3). The objective of this study is to evaluate the prevalence of upper and lower respiratory tract infections among patients presenting in the medical outdoor department.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This study was conducted among the patients presenting in the outdoor medical department of different hospitals. Name, age, gender and history and duration of respiratory tract infection were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 26.0. The quantitative variables, i.e., age, duration of infection was presented as mean and standard deviation. The qualitative variables, i.e., gender, the prevalence of upper and lower respiratory tract infection, were presented as frequency and percentages.

RESULTS:

A total of 98 patients were included in this study. The mean age of the patients was 34.98 ± 4.23 years. There were 43 males and 55 females. There were 15 (35%) males and 42 (65%) females who presented with upper respiratory tract infections. There were 29 (65%) males and 13 (24%) females who presented with lower respiratory tract infections. The mean duration of infection was 5.78 ± 2.34 days.

DISCUSSION:

Treatment comprises symptomatic support usually via analgesics for headache, sore throat, and muscle aches. Moderate exercise in sedentary subjects with a naturally acquired URTI probably does not alter the overall severity and duration of the illness. No randomized trials have been conducted to ascertain benefits of increasing fluid intake. Prescribing antibiotics for laryngitis is not a suggested practice. The antibiotics penicillin V and erythromycin are not effective for treating acute laryngitis. Erythromycin may

improve voice disturbances after a week and cough after 2 weeks, but any modest subjective benefit is not greater than the adverse effects, cost, and the risk of bacteria developing resistance to the antibiotics. Health authorities have been strongly encouraging physicians to decrease the prescribing of antibiotics to treat common URTIs because antibiotic usage does not significantly reduce recovery time for these viral illnesses. A 2017 systematic review found three interventions which were probably effective in reducing antibiotic use for acute respiratory infections: C-reactive protein testing, procalcitonin-guided management, and shared decision-making between physicians and patients. The use of narrow-spectrum antibiotics has been shown to be just as effective as broad-spectrum alternatives for children with acute bacterial URTIs and has a lower risk of side effects in children. Antibiotics do not help the many lower respiratory infections which are caused by parasites or viruses. While acute bronchitis often does not require antibiotic therapy, antibiotics can be given to patients with acute exacerbations of chronic bronchitis. The indications for treatment are increased dyspnea, and an increase in the volume or purulence of the sputum. The treatment of bacterial pneumonia is selected by considering the age of the patient, the severity of the illness and the presence of underlying disease. A systematic review of 32 randomized controlled trials with 6,078 participants with acute respiratory infections compared procalcitonin (a blood marker for bacterial infections) to guide the initiation and duration of antibiotic treatment, against no use of procalcitonin. Among 3,336 people receiving procalcitonin-guided antibiotic therapy, there were 236 deaths, compared to 336 deaths out 3,372 participants who did not. Procalcitonin-guided antibiotic therapy also reduced the antibiotic use duration by 2.4 days, and there were fewer antibiotic side effects. This means that procalcitonin is useful for guiding whether to use antibiotics for acute respiratory infections and the duration of the antibiotic. Amoxicillin and doxycycline are suitable for many of the lower respiratory tract infections seen in general practice. Another cochrane review suggests that new studies are needed to confirm that

azithromycin may lead to less treatment failure and lower side effects than amoxicillin. In the other hand, there is no sufficient evidence to consider the antibiotics as a prophylaxis for the high-risk children under 12 years (4-6).

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